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INCLUSIVE PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES WITH CHILDREN WITH AUTISTIC SPECTRUM DISORDER IN EARLY EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Diversity is an approach that needs to be worked on with a focus on building an inclusive and egalitarian society. The school must help prepare people to exercise their citizenship. The objective of this study is to analyze how educators deal with the challenges of including children with autism in early childhood education. Thus, as the importance of public policies, continued training, adaptation resources and appropriate teaching materials aimed at enriching the educational practices of teachers in early childhood education, aimed at an education capable of promoting well-being and valuing diversity, respect for differences and promotion of opportunities with equity. Educational institutions can create an inclusive and welcoming teaching environment for children with autism, with the aim of fostering improvements in learning.